

Reproduction of Experimental Results

“How Do Gain and Discount Functions Affect the Correlation between DCG and User Satisfaction?”

Group #45

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About the paper

DCG (Discounted Cumulative Gain) is a metric used to measure the ranking quality of search engine.

It determines whether the items we get from search engine are relevant to the customer (*cumulative function*) and rewards a search engine that boosts relevant items near the top of the sort (*discount function*).

The authors of the paper analyzed 36 combinations of gain and discount to find the best correlated functions with user satisfaction level.

How Do Gain and Discount Functions Affect the Correlation between DCG and User Satisfaction?

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Abstract. We present an empirical analysis of the effect that the gain and discount functions have in the correlation between *DCG* and user satisfaction. Through a large user study we estimate the relationship between satisfaction and the effectiveness computed with a test collection. In particular, we estimate the probabilities that users find a system satisfactory given a *DCG* score, and that they agree with a difference in *DCG* as to which of two systems is more satisfactory. We study this relationship for 36 combinations of gain and discount, and find that a linear gain and a constant discount are best correlated with user satisfaction.

1 Introduction

Test collections are used to evaluate how well systems help users in an Information Retrieval task. In conjunction with an effectiveness measure such as Average Precision, they are an abstraction of the search process that allows us to systematically evaluate and improve systems by assessing how good a system is, and which of two systems is better. In particular, collections are an abstraction of the static component in the search process (e.g., documents, topical relevance), while effectiveness measures are an abstraction of the dynamic component (e.g., user behavior, interactions between documents). This user abstraction is advantageous because it makes evaluation experiments inexpensive, easy to run, and easy to reproduce. However, they make several assumptions about how users interact with a system and the perceived utility of the documents it retrieves.

Imagine a system that obtains an effectiveness score $\phi \in [0, 1]$ for some query. The best we can interpret ϕ is to assume that $\phi \cdot 100\%$ of users will be satisfied by the system, or $P(\text{Sat}|\phi) = \phi$. If we obtain $DCG = 0.85$, we somehow interpret it as 85% probability of user satisfaction. Similarly, if the difference between two systems A and B is $\Delta\phi > 0$, we expect users to agree and prefer A over B. In fact, we expect them to do so *regardless* of how large $\Delta\phi$ is, or $P(\text{Pref}|\Delta\phi) = 1$. If the test collection tells us that A is superior to B, we expect users to agree. The extent to which these interpretations are valid depends on whether the assumptions mentioned above hold or not. For instance, relevance judgments are subjective, meaning that we should expect $P(\text{Pref}|\Delta\phi) < 1$. Similarly, different effectiveness measures are based on different user models and thus result in different ϕ scores, so $P(\text{Sat}|\phi) = \phi$ is not necessarily true.

Experiment workflow

Assumption (Research goal) is that the correlation between DCG and User Satisfaction can help in finding differences between two different search engines and advise which one of them is better than the other.

Dataset (Data) consists of 4115 preference responses provided by 113 users. Responses indicate whether (1) system A, (2) system B, (3) both systems or (4) no system is considered satisfactory.

In 2025 of these 4115 records, both or none of the systems were satisfactory while the remaining 2090 records preference for one of the systems.

Instructions

Imagine you could use a service where you provide a clip of music as a query and the service then recommends five songs similar to it. In this task we give you an arbitrary query and the songs recommended by two different services. You have to listen to the songs and tell us what service provided better results.

Query

Service A Service B

What service gives better results?

Service A
 Service B
 They are both equally good
 They are both equally bad

Any comments?

Submit

Reproduction workflow


```
func_one <- function(test_mode = F) {  
  print(getwd())  
  basic_dir <- "output"  
  fig_dir <- paste0(basic_dir, "/",fig)  
  biases_dir <- paste0(basic_dir, "/biases.csv")  
  if(test_mode) {  
    fig_dir <- paste0(fig_dir, "_")  
    ret <- unlink(paste0(fig_dir, "1"), recursive = T)  
    ret <- unlink(paste0(fig_dir, "2"), recursive = T)  
    biases_dir <- sub("biases", "biases_", biases_dir)  
    ret <- unlink(biases_dir, recursive = T)  
  }  
  source("src/common.R")  
  
  # Prepare output  
  dir.create(paste0(fig_dir, "1"), recursive = T, showWarnings = F)  
  dir.create(paste0(fig_dir, "2"), recursive = T, showWarnings = F)  
  
  # Read data  
  df <- read.csv("data/crowd.csv", stringsAsFactors = F)  
  
  # Data frame to store bias scores (computed while plotting, analyzed after)  
  biases <- NULL  
  count <- 0  
  
  # P(Sat | phi) =====  
  # Iterate discount functions  
  for (discount in split(discounts, 1:nrow(discounts))) {  
    # Initialize plot  
    my.dev.new(paste0(fig_dir, "1/sat-vs-", discount$id, ".pdf"))  
    plot(NA, main = paste(discount$name, "discount"),  
         xlim = 0:1, xaxs = "i", xlab = expression(phi),  
         ylim = 0:1, yaxs = "i", ylab = expression(hat(P)*("Sat | "phi*)))  
    abline(0:1, col = "grey")
```

Intermediate results

Analysis of the Github repository structure

Verifying data input □ 4,115 examples covering 432 unique queries,
5,636 unique documents with 2025/2090 records per class

Verifying data visualization

- Fig. 1. (6 plots) - estimated with 2025 records judging both systems as good or bad for all DCG combinations
- Fig. 2. (6 plots) - estimated with 2090 records judging one of the system better than the other
- Fig. 3. (3 boxplots) - 3 different biases for each D/G-function

Test methodology

- Adding a test-parameter for the output, that is to be generated in a separate folder, than the original output folder, so a comparison between the original plots and pdfs can be done.
- The original data itself will not be manipulated and stays untouched.

Verifying bias scores □ The comparison of the output of all bias functions shows, that the output-data throughout the test-run is identical to the original data.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Challenges

Real-time collaboration in the browser platform

- Deepnote!

Extension of original paper to confirm/validate outcomes

Corresponding R-Code was not mentioned in the paper so we had to explore the web.

- Found the full project in Github

Author(s) did **not share the model** and **generated records**.

Label	Data		Platform / Stack	Implementation	Method	Research Objective	Actor	Gain
	Parameters	Raw Data						
Repeat	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Determinism
Param. Sweep	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	Robustness / Sensitivity
Generalize	(x)	x	-	-	-	-	-	Applicability across different settings
Port	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	Portability across platforms, flexibility
Re-code	-	-	(x)	x	-	-	-	Correctness of implementation, flexibility, adoption, efficiency
Validate	(x)	(x)	(x)	(x)	x	-	-	Correctness of hypothesis, validation via different approach
Re-use	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	Apply code in different settings, Re-purpose
Independent x (orthogonal)							x	Sufficiency of information, independent verification

Remaining work...

- **Further validation of original outcomes** using different random seed settings in R, varying number of bins and predictions, and as well as subsets of the data.
- **Completion of the final report** following the ACM formatting guidelines.

References

- [Julian-urbano/ecir2015-dcg: Reproduce results from the ECIR 2015 paper "How do Gain and Discount Functions Affect the Correlation between DCG and User Satisfaction?" \(github.com\)](#)
- [Reproducibility of Data-Oriented Experiments in e-Science](#)
- [The PRIMAD Model of Reproducibility](#)